

PARAMETRLI NOSIMMETRIK RSA SHIFRLASH ALGORITMINI GENERATSIYA QILISH DASTURI

Qarshiboyev Nizomiddin Abdumalik o'g'li

Jizzax politexnika instituti "ICHJA va B" kafedrası, v.b., dotsent

Email: wolkswagen1991@gmail.com

Annotatsiya: Ushbu dasturiy ta'minotni yaratishda zamonaviy dasturiy vositalari (muhitini) dan foydalanib yaratish, ularning imkoniyatlaridan foydalanish va dasturiy vositalarning universalligi, soddaligi va tarmoqda ishlay oladigan tomonlari o'rganilgan. Microsoft Visual Studio 2008 dasturi Microsoft korporatsiyasi tomonidan ishlab chiqilgan bo'lib, bu dastur dasturchilar uchun mo'ljallangandir.

Kalit so'zlar: Microsoft korporatsiyasi, Microsoft Visual Studio 2008 muhiti, Visual C#, Visual Basic, Visual J# tillari, Web dasturlar, Visual C#, Visual Basic, Visual J#, Visual C++, Windows muhiti, dastur.

Аннотация: При создании данного программного обеспечения изучались создание с использованием современных программных средств (среды), использование их возможностей, универсальность, простота и возможность работы в сети. Microsoft Visual Studio 2008 разработан корпорацией Microsoft и предназначен для разработчиков.

Ключевые слова: корпорация Microsoft, среда Microsoft Visual Studio 2008, Visual C#, Visual Basic, языки Visual J#, веб-приложения, Visual C#, Visual Basic, Visual J#, Visual C++, среда Windows, программа.

Abstract: In the creation of this software, creation using modern software tools (environment), use of their capabilities, universality, simplicity of software tools, and aspects of being able to work on the network were studied. Microsoft Visual Studio 2008 was developed by Microsoft Corporation and is intended for developers.

Keywords: Microsoft Corporation, Microsoft Visual Studio 2008 environment, Visual C#, Visual Basic, Visual J# languages, Web applications, Visual C#, Visual Basic, Visual J#, Visual C++, Windows environment, program.

Microsoft Visual Studio 2008 dasturi yordamida Windows muhiti uchun, telefonlar uchun, tarmoqlar uchun, Web dasturlarni yaratish mumkin. Microsoft Visual Studio 2008 muhitida Visual C#, Visual Basic, Visual J# tillari yordamida Web dasturlarni va Visual C#, Visual Basic, Visual J#, Visual C++ tillari yordamida Windows muhiti uchun dasturlar yaratish mumkin.

C# dasturlash tilining afzallik taraflari shundaki, bu dasturlash tilida juda ko'plab kutubxonalar bor. Bu kutubxonalar dasturchi uchun qulaylik tug'diribgina qolmasdan,

kam hato qilishga olib keladi. C# dasturlash .NET Freamwork kutubxonalarini bilan ishlaydi. [5]

Biz dastur tuzishda C# dasturlash tilidan foydalandik. Bu dastur Visual Studio umumiy paketiga kiradi. Hamda Microsoft firmasi tomonidan ishlab chiqilgan. Shuning bilan bu dastur faqat Microsoft, Macintosh operatsion muhitlarida ishlaydi. Bu dastur ishlashi uchun bir talay qo‘shimcha dasturlar kerak bo‘ladi.

Parametrlar algebrasi asosida takomillashtirilgan El-Gamal shifrlash algoritmining dasturi quyida keltirilgan.

Dasturda oshkora p , a parametrlar, e_i , d_j maxfiy kalitlar, aloqa kanalidagi i -, j -tomonlarning maxfiy kalitlari va r_{ij} – aloqa kanalida i -, j -tomonlarning parametr sifatida foydalanadigan o‘zaro maxfiy yoki oshkora kaliti hamda k_i , k_j – aloqa kanalida i -, j -tomonlarning mos tarzda har aloqa seansida tasodifiy son sifatida tanlanadigan maxfiy seans kalitlari generatsiya qilinadi. [6]

Dastur quyidagi bandlardan iborat:

1. Kalit generatori bandi. Ushbu bandda RSA shifrlash algoritmi uchun kerakli bo‘lgan kalitlar avtomatik ravishda hosil qilinadi.

The screenshot shows a software window titled "Parametrlar El-Gamal" with a blue background. It contains several sections for parameter input and generation:

- Section 1:**
 - P (256 bit): 893401566039117783577248357787852304171966778462172456511767647
 - a (192 bit): 3963223657804864027350334027097389671053481075539860454153
 - Buttons: AutGen
- Section 2:**
 - $e(i)$ (192 bit): 4927291207159112435302415170012031098199413942306469299649
 - $d(j)$ (192 bit): 6230925012475601809077044765187007667592477440789913260621
 - Buttons: AutGen
- Section 3:**
 - $r(i)$ (8 bit): 149
 - $r(j)$ (8 bit): 191
 - $r(ij)=r(i)+r(j)(\text{mod } P)$: 340
 - Buttons: AutGen
- Section 4:**
 - $k(i)$ (192 bit): 4669649089170314669719493387409347321587511142352172475047
 - $k(j)$ (192 bit): 498352925252045397769772761903684407392971671280275999123
 - Buttons: AutGen
- Section 5:**
 - $y(i)$: 770538685754528181775054268447130116565859084857098551253933017
 - $y(j)$: 386641130800324976575793400338458752344953617134908939405397138
 - Buttons: Calculate
- Section 6:**
 - Matn: [Text input field]
 - S (1): [Text input field]
 - S (2): [Text input field]
 - Dastlabki matn: [Text input field]
 - Buttons: Encryption, Decryption

1-rasm. Kalit generatsiyasi

2. Axborotni shifrlash jarayoni bandi. Ushbu bandda yaratilgan kalitlar asosida kiritilgan matnni shifrlash amalga oshiriladi. Misol uchun yaratilgan kalitlar bilan “Mumunova Mastura Maxmudjon qizi” matnini shifrlaymiz. Oynada axborotning shifr matni hosil bo‘ladi.

The screenshot shows a software application window titled "Parametrlil_EL_Gamal" with a blue border. It contains several sections for generating encryption parameters and performing encryption/decryption:

- Shifrlash parametrlari:** Fields for P (256 bit) and a (192 bit), both containing long hexadecimal strings. An "AutGen" button is to the right.
- Tasdiq kalitlari:** Fields for $e(i)$ (192 bit) and $d(i)$ (192 bit), both containing long hexadecimal strings. An "AutGen" button is to the right.
- Kalitlar kashfiyotining moduli kabin:** Fields for $r(i)$ (8 bit) with values 149 and 191, and a field for $r(i)=r(i)+r(i)(\text{mod}P)$ with value 340. An "AutGen" button is to the right.
- Moduli bo‘lmas kalitlari:** Fields for $k(i)$ (192 bit) and $k(i)$ (192 bit), both containing long hexadecimal strings. An "AutGen" button is to the right.
- Tasdiq bo‘lmas:** Fields for $y(i)$ with values 770538685754528181775054268447130116565859084857098551253933017 and 386641130800324976575793400338458752344953617134908939405397138. A "Calculate" button is to the right.
- Seans bosqich (Shifrlash va Dastlabki):** A text field containing "Mumunova Mastura Maxmudjon qizi". Below it are fields for $S(1)$ and $S(2)$ with long hexadecimal strings. A "Dastlabki matn" field is at the bottom. "Encryption" and "Decryption" buttons are on the right.

2-rasm. Axborotni shifrlash jarayoni

3. Axborotning shifrini ochish jarayoni bandi. Ushbu bandda hosil qilingan shifr matnni ochiq matnga aylantirish masalasi ko‘rib chiqiladi. Buning uchun *Shifrnı ochish tugmasi bosiladi va dastur* oynasida ochiq matn “Mumunova Mastura Maxmudjon qizi” hosil bo‘ladi.

3-rasm. Axborotning shifrini ochish jarayoni

Ishlab chiqilgan nosimmetrik shifrlash algoritmi qo‘shimcha maxfiylik sifatida R parametri kiritilishi hisoblash murakkabligi ortadi. Bu esa ishlab chiqilgan algoritmlarning bardoshliligi yuqoriligidan dalolat beradi.

Xulosa: Ishlab chiqilgan takomillashtirigan shifrlash algoritmidan va dasturidan O‘zbekiston Respublikasida shakllanayotgan elektron hukumat tizimida ma’lumotlar bazalarini va axborot-kommunikatsiya tarmoqlari orqali uzatiladigan ma’lumotlarni konfidentsialligini ta’minlash jarayonida foydalanilish xavfsizlikni yuqori darajada ta’minlash uchun imkon yaratadi.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar ro'yxati:

1. Shlixt G.Yu. Tsifrovaya obrabotka tsvetno'x izobrajeniy. - M., Izdatelstvo EKOM, 1997. - 336 s.
2. Yane, B. Tsifrovaya obrabotka izobrajeniy G' B. Yane: per. s angl. pod red. A.M. Izmaylovoy. M.: Texnosfera, 2007 - 584s.-ISBN 978-5-94836122-2
3. [Kravchenko V.F.](#) Tsifrovaya obrabotka signalov i izobrajeniy. - M.: [FIZMATLIT](#), 2007 g.
4. Axbutayevich, T.S., & Abdumalikovich, Q.N. (2022). IMAGE CONTOUR SEPARATION ALGORITHMS BASED ON THE THEORY OF FUZZY SETS. International Journal of Contemporary Scientific and Technical Research, 120-125.
5. Axbutayevich, T.S., & Abdumalikovich, Q.N. (2022). TASVIRLARDAN MA'LUMOT OLIISHDA MATLAB MUHITINING INTELLEKTUAL TASHKIL ETUVCHILARIDAN FOYDALANISH. International Journal of Contemporary Scientific and Technical Research, 247-250.
6. Akhbutayevich, T. S., & Abdumalikovich, K. N. (2022). Algorithms for Selecting the Contour Lines of Images Based on the Theory of Fuzzy Sets. Texas Journal of Engineering and Technology, 15, 31-40.
7. Savurbaev, A., Dangalov, N.A., Shertoylov, G.M., & Eshonkulov, Sh.U. (2014). Algoritm rascheta perexodnogo protsessa pri udare tsilindrisheskogo koltsa o jestkoe poluprostranstvo. *Molodoy ucheno'y*, (8), 246-250.
8. Eshonkulov, Sh., Burliev, A., & Eshonkulova, Sh. (2019). Nauchno-metodicheskiy podxod k sozdaniyu elektronnoy uchebnika.
9. Savurbaev, A., Muxammadiev, M.T., Eshankulov, Sh.U., & Guliev, A.A. (2015). Kosoy udar tsilindrisheskogo koltsa o jestkoe poluprostranstvo. *Molodoy ucheno'y*, (1), 97-102.